

COMMON LICHENS ON STONE, CONCRETE, SIDEWALKS, AND WALLS

Lichens are the cooperative partnership between a fungus and many partners, including at least one or more algae and/or cyanobacteria. The thallus (body) of a lichen is made of a fungus that positions the photosynthetic partner in a thin layer near the surface where it is exposed to sunlight. The partner photosynthesizes and provides the fungus with nutrients.

Many of the species found on stone are crustose species. Crustose is a thin and crusty growth form of lichen, fully attached to the surface it grows on instead of separated by a skin-like bottom layer.

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Cross section of a lichen:
A) upper cortex, B) algal layer, C) medulla,
D) lower cortex, E) rhizines

Lichens are all around you. They can grow on all sorts of surfaces (called substrates) such as: rock, concrete, bark, bare ground, metal, and more. Lichens do not harm the plants they grow on but they can wear away stone very slowly.

Symbols used here:

: Where you'll find it

: Appearance and key features

Caloplaca flavocitrina Flakey Firedots

: Somewhat common on concrete walls, especially shaded wet areas.

: Crustose, yellow to yellow green. From a distance this species looks like a dense patch or smear of yellow soredia on a wall.

There are many kinds of small yellow lichens on concrete. Compare the granular soredia above to the red apothecia of *C. oxfordensis* (left) and the uniform yellow of *C. aurella* (right).

Five common rock lichens in Mid-Atlantic and Northeast cities and towns

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Candelariella vitellina
Common Goldspecks

: On sunny rocks.

: Thallus lumpy and clustered, yellow.

Discs round, yellow to dark yellow, rims same color or slightly lighter than discs. Forms clustered clumps separated by deep ridges.

Lecanora dispersa
Mortar Rim

: Very common on sidewalks, cement, and stone walls.

: Crustose, thallus immersed and indistinct. Apothecia typically clustered, discs reddish brown to brown, rims white, 0.3-1.0 mm. One of the most common species, it is difficult to see because of its diminutive size.

Candelariella aurella
Hidden Goldspecks

: Very commonly found on cement walls and sidewalks.

: Apothecia very tiny yellow disks, rims bumpy and irregular, of the same color as the disc, 0.2-0.5 mm.

Caloplaca feracissima
Sidewalk Firedots

: Very commonly found on cement sidewalks and buildings.

: Thallus immersed and indistinct.

Apothecia common, discs orange to yellow orange; rim lighter yellow than disc, 0.2-0.5 mm. One of the easiest to spot in cities, it is differentiated from *C. aurella* by its darker discs and smooth rims.

There are many other lichen species that grow on walls and stone that are not crustose. They are usually larger, have a 'leaf-like' appearance, and can be scratched away from their substrate easily. To identify these species consult other pamphlets in this series covering foliose lichens.